

PLANINNG AND ENGAGEMENT ARENAS FOR RENEWABLE ENERGY LANDSCAPES

PEARLS

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Abstract:

This deliverable contains a short description of the PEARLS Project website (PPW), including the construction of the PPW by participants in WP1 PEARLS INTERACTION PLATFORM under the supervision of the coordinator. The website will run throughout the project to present research achievements, staff exchange results, publications and news and events. An On-Line Atlas has been created for fieldwork activities and results. The public section of the PPW will be disseminated to the general public through social media (i.e., Facebook, Twitter, Instagram and Pinterest).

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I. Introduction

This deliverable describes the PEARLS Project website (PPW). The PPW's main goal is to strengthen external communication and to develop and implement tools that facilitate participants' day-to-day work on the Project. The PPW is one of the main objectives of Work Package 1 PEARLS INTERACTION PLATFORM. WP1's first task is a data sharing platform, with key information on the project and contact information for all partners. The public section of the project website is for public communication.

The Pearls Project Website provides:

- The project-related information and news.
- A description of work packages and their goals.
- An Online Atlas that displays on screen the main fieldwork results of staff exchange through secondments.
- A repository used to store Deliverables, PEARLS members' publications and other documents.
- A Good-to-Know section with events and other activities.

The following sections of this document present on the tools involved in the WPs.

II. Website implementation

The implementation of the Pearls Project website was completed using Wordpress and Divi Builder system. Wordpress is a world well-known and widely used CMS that allows a faster prototyping in both design and functionality. In addition is highly compatible and works with w3c standards. Divi builder system provides adaptability easy designs while working. It also gives the opportunity to see changes in real time integrated into a production system. This way it is flexible to accommodate changes and future needs. In this combination of Wordpress and Divi Builder every element is placed where we want to make more visual and well organized contents for the visitors. Also Wordpress assures the perfect combination of technology and compatibility with major browsers and the expandability of future needs for the Pearls project website. It's consistent and his periodically updates work well with software changes in the future without affecting functionality.

1. Website standards compliance

Pearls Project website pages have been tested to comply with the HTML5 standard, using the W3C Markup Validator. Even though the PWW comply with both the CSS and CSS3 standards, the situation is more complicated in regards to CSS. We have chosen to use CSS3 for the Pearls Project website because it simplifies the implementation of aesthetic elements such as rounded element corners, element shadows etc...

However, the CSS3 standard is currently and will be a work in progress. So, while we have taken every care for our CSS code, it has been proved impossible to have CSS3 code that both validates on the W3C CSS Validator and works on all popular browsers. This made us take a more pragmatic approach and instead strive to have our pages rendered correctly with the latest versions of all popular web browsers.

2. Hosting

For the Pearls Project website we have chosen Raiola Networks, a Spanish company, which deliver fast and reliable hosting services from their servers in France. It has also proven reliability, secure functioning and fast work with their SSD hostings.

3. Hardware

The Pearls Project website is hosted by Raiola Networks services, their servers are located in France. The hosting server features a total memory of 1024mb ultra fast ram memory. 5GB of solid state drive space, which increases the speed of delivered data. The Raiola servers are based on Linux and provide SSL certified by Let's Encrypt.

The server is protected by firewalls in order to minimize the risk of cyber-threats. As an additional security measure, Raiola Network provides a security copy every day in case of any malfunction.

4. Software

For serving the PEARLS Project website we use this software stack:

- CloudLinux as the operating system
- Apache as the web server
- PHP for dynamic interactive web page support
- MySQL as the database backend
- Wordpress as CMS
- Divi Builder System as Design framework inside Wordpress

All the components of the stack have been built in one server. The server is dedicated to running the MySQL server, the Apache web server and generate the dynamic pages using Wordpress CMS. Wordpress is a generic web framework based in PHP and MySQL. For serving and managing our pages we use Wordpress a Content Management System and for designing we use Divi Builder System, is a modular theme framework. The benefit of the Divi Builder and Wordpress combo is that they provide a clear, well documented Application designing interface. They are much more compact and updated than other solutions, which make tweaking and extending them much easier. This could prove useful in case we need to extend the functionality of the Pearls Project website beyond the initial standards and requirements. An additional benefit of this combo is the existing expertise of the Divi and Wordpress supporters dedicated to maintaining and improving the Wordpress code.

Finally, it should be noticed that all the software components will be regularly updated. This way security vulnerabilities will be kept at a minimum level.

5. Website description and screenshots

The Pearls Project website can be found at <http://pearlsproject.org/>

The PPW is organised into different user-friendly sections that can be easily navigated and updated. This is due in part to the photographs of renewable energy landscapes provided by PEARLS members.

The website is divided into six main sections:

- **HOME**
- **ABOUT US**
- **WORK PACKAGES**
- **ONLINE ATLAS**
- **RESOURCES**
- **GOOD TO KNOW**

The following gives information about the initial design of the site together with a brief explanation of its aim and contents.

Home

This section provides an overview of the Pearls Project: the scroll feature can be used to read through its mission and headline statement, geographical coverage, cultural diversity, project structure and a ‘Contact Us’ form. Geographical coverage and cultural diversity are represented through historical maps, interesting images and original texts on or closely-related to renewable energies, provided by the consortium as a whole. The project structure presents the logos of the thirteen participants together with the Advisory Board members’ names and logos. Finally, the ‘Contact Us’ form links to EUSOCLAB at the University of Seville (Spain), which is the body responsible for constructing and maintaining the website.

About us

This section contains information about the research project, partners, the team and secondments.

._ The Project

This sub-section contains detailed information about the research and innovation skills and abilities of the Pearls Project. A variety of layouts with vertical scrolling include the following:

- Summary
- Participants
- Relevance
- Aims and objectives
- Research Questions
- Impact
- Ethics
- Gender Balance

Summary

As an active key actor in the spatial planning and social innovation arena for Renewable Energy Landscapes REL, the PEARLS project will reinforce the population's commitment to secure, clean and efficient energy. REL are regarded as spaces where renewable energies change the population's relationship with energy and their landscape perception. Despite all efforts, resistance to REL lingers in Europe, while the reasons for strong social acceptance in Mediterranean and South American countries are still unknown. Thus PEARLS will focus on Southern European countries and Israel due to their wealth of renewable energy resources and citizens' deep engagement with REL.

PEARLS main goal is to develop applied knowledge through question about how to increase public engagement in the benefit of sustainable-renewable energy system through planning processes. Its results will transform policy initiatives and strategic interventions with the population, in places where energy resources are relevant and local communities are disadvantaged that networking offers. Using secondment, staff exchange and collaborative research, the project will investigate on national legal basis, will develop methodologies on social innovation, and will explore tools from the multidisciplinary approach of Social Sciences in different European regions. Budget conditions will reinforce research and innovation staff exchange from the academic and non-academic sector, sharing resources from the implementation of the project within all the participants.

PEARLS is radically transforming scientific knowledge on how to best implement REL across Europe and extend southern landscapes towards other Mediterranean countries through participant networks. PEARLS will generate a step change in the way that REL are theorized, defined and addressed and provide crucial support for the European Energy Challenge by establishing international, intersectoral and multidisciplinary collaboration on the basis of a five-country hub-and-spoke of activities and research centres in close cooperation with non-academic sectors. All Partner by members from five universities and nine non-academic beneficiaries (private consultancies, cooperatives and business associations) have proven expertise and experience in working with renewable energy policy, REL, spatial planning and social innovation, through the internationalisation of applied research and training for capacity development. Via secondments, staff exchange and collaborative inquiry, the project will investigate how to reinforce renewable energy best practice to contribute to the Energy Challenge. Deliverables will be provided by working reports, websites, toolkits, training and methodology materials, seminars, and scientific papers, academic journals and books.

The academic Partnership is between seven universities (Seville, Lisbon, Torino, Thessaloniki and Huelva) and seven non-academic organisations (industry organisations and business, small and medium companies, government agencies and civil society organisations such as non-profit) from Southern European countries. The entire consortium has strong expertise and research capacity to produce deliverables in the form of seminars, public S&ME maps, training materials, guidelines on environmental impact assessment, internationalization of legal frameworks, websites resource bases, best practices on effective and inclusive public participation, working papers and academic journal articles. In addition to research capacity development, PEARLS will consolidate existing links and forge new connectors for future research applications to the European Union and beyond in issues of renewable energy landscapes.

Who is undertaking the project?

The Consortium consists of 13 academic and non-academic entities from Portugal, Spain, Italy, Greece and Israel, and 3 non-academic entities from Spain, United Kingdom and Italy that will support the Consortium as an Advisory Board. All participating organisations have been selected for their diverse, complementary expertise and together in planning and public engagement in renewable energy in Southern European countries and Israel. All are highly internationalised organisations in the Mediterranean Basin and have a proven ability to go the extra mile!

The management structure comprises:

- The overall Project Coordinator based in Seville, who acts between the Consortium and the Funding Authority and acts as the Chair of the work.
- The Steering Committee, which is a body composed of all Work Package leaders and/or leaders (ICIKL, CLANER, APTI and TER) and is established as the consortium's ultimate decision-making body.
- The Partnership Board that includes one representative of each beneficiary of the Project.
- The Advisory Board as an external body which supports and advises the Steering Committee and the Coordinator. The academic and non-academic organisations that belong to this body are the Italian National Agency for New Technologies (INAI), Prodel (Spain) and Exten University (United Kingdom).

The Coordinator is supported by a team comprised by the Research Financial Service, Senior Academic Staff, Technical Research Assistants, Doctoral Candidates and Administrative Staff. Finally, the Management Support Team works as administrative assistant to the Partnership Board, the Coordinator and the Steering Committee and manages the day-to-day management of the Project.

The European Social Research Laboratory (ESORLAB) at the University of Seville coordinates the overall project, working with PEARLS partners to define research design, theoretical frameworks and data collection methods and analysis for all WP. ESORLAB members have considerable expertise in developing teaching and research REL, spatial planning and social analysis in Southern Europe. They have conducted research on spatial planning, environmental analysis, public engagement and REL in Southern Spain and research programs in academic. ESORLAB has a range of international staff and also postgraduate students. It is located in the University of Seville's International Centre, which provides resources for international staff and students.

The Coordinator is responsible for overseeing planning, organizing, motivating, controlling resources, procedures and methods to achieve the deliverables and answer the project's research questions. The project is strategically managed to ensure that the deliverables match expectations and objectives and that the end product functions effectively. This involves rigorous scheduling, risk and financial management as well as the understanding of quality assurance into all processes, procedures and products from the study's peer review, data back-up plans and contingency planning.

ICIKL - Instituto de Ciencia Social multi-reports in social sciences research. Thus, it plays a key role in RPIPS, Social Innovation and Public Engagement. ICIKL will send researchers to cooperate in studying and implementing public engagement with renewable energies, and also to government organisations to collect information on legislation, policy and planning tools. ICIKL will also provide training on social research to participating members.

UNITEC - The Department of Civil, Environmental and Mechanical Engineering at Torino University works on spatial and landscape planning and renewable energies. Social issues related to energy technologies will be addressed in conjunction with the Department of Sociology and Social Research. University staff will cooperate on international projects, providing expertise in different fields, and applied research in spatial planning and landscape protection.

APTI - Aikateo Observatory of Thessaloniki is the largest public Greek Observatory, is committed to conducting high quality research in a diverse field of academic and promoting quality and excellence. The APTI team has proven ability with a long number (more than 3500) peer-reviewed publications in high quality journals and national and international conferences. The experience of APTI team members involved in the project has also been demonstrated by their involvement in international research collaboration (FP7 projects) and in international collaboration research (e.g., Temes, COST) that enhances the team's scientific and research capabilities.

BOU - Ben Gurion University of the Negev will contribute to building awareness and the legal regulation aspects of land use planning in particular they will study and assess different aspects of renewable energy locations, including landscape impact, institutional capacities and public participation in planning. The Israeli academic partner will be able to host project members for cross-national data gathering and analysis and cooperation in networking events.

COOP - Cooperativa Portuguesa Renováveis Energia Cooperative (190 members in 2017) that combines its sustainability-oriented and social nature with support for industry, education and environmental protection programs. Secondment within its focus on citizen and business engagement in the creation of an energy, economic and social paradigm that benefits both society and the environment: renewable, efficient, fair, democratic and decentralised. Other relevant activities include the promotion of best practices in energy use to their members in order that they might contribute to a more sustainable future by using green electricity in their homes or companies. Furthermore, it also challenges people to show concern for the environment and society and empowers them as citizens and decision-makers in the area of energy production.

ENEC - Enerconistas is an Association of Solar Energy Companies in Southern Portugal with extensive experience in managing demonstration innovative technology clusters in different scales, operating on a large and produce platforms in the field of photovoltaics and solar water systems. They have developed a high ability to carry through all projects in the area of renewable energy, system integration with national level support.

CLANER - Cluster de Energias Renováveis is a cluster of companies, official bodies, research centres, universities and foundations in the area of renewable energies and energy efficiency in Southern Spain. It is a non-profit Association and works as an organisational alliance of renewable energy firms. The Cluster has secured one hundred members (SMEs, Multinationals, Universities, Research Centres, public bodies and foundations) and represents more 100% of the renewable sector in the South of Spain. CLANER promotes research, technological development and innovation in projects, processes and services linked to it, while also fostering cooperation among its members, provides an excellent network of multidisciplinary expertise and a methodological approach through engineering, planning, assistance, training, maintenance and supply in renewable energy and energy efficiency.

TERE - Territorio 4.0 is a firm that provides experience in the field of spatial and visual landscape analysis and operates as research advisor to regional and local administrations using self-developed methodological tools. Areas of expertise include: Landscape Character Assessment, Visual Impact Assessment, topological analysis and the identification of visual sensitive resources, all by means of GIS use combined with fieldwork and qualitative methods. TERE has the capacity to host secondments in its area of expertise and to contribute to conceptual and analytical framework to related to landscape and heritage management and communication and dissemination activities, and project management support.

GRI - Geosystems Italia will design and implement a geographic information system which will be the basis for recording project geographical data and any information derived from the data. GIS capabilities will offer a user-friendly environment to easily and quickly access the required information and to retrieve when necessary to identify and make any corrections required in the study area. GRI will update the PEARLS project website. It will be available to transfer knowledge to the participating organisations via on-site, written training and project site questionnaires. An online manual will be made available. The company will participate in the project events and also to cooperate with participating organisations interested in technology transfer.

AKKT - AKKT Engineering is a Greek high-tech company and consultancy that also provides services for managing and delivering government and private sector projects and advisory services, mainly in the areas of urban and spatial planning, architectural design, environmental engineering, hydro-geo-engineering, geomatics, land surveying and photogrammetry, and creates 3D mapping projects. The company has also been involved in an implemented developer for several projects in Europe. Territorial Cooperation, Cross Border and other Programmes that involve research innovation in spatial, strategic and environmental planning.

TC&E - T&E Consultants & Engineers is a Greek company with experience and expertise in the development and implementation of IT projects and new technologies in both public and private sector enterprises and organisations. The company provides comprehensive IT consulting services including analysis and strategic planning of information systems, planning and support in energy applications, development and application of information systems and new technologies - geo-information, management of resources, mapping, spatial analysis, databases, GIS development and adaptation, training and support.

SPR - Science Policy Interface is a team of research and consultancy group that links science to real life in the government, the business sector and NGOs. Its main goal is to integrate scientific knowledge and considerations into the government. The group specialises in environmental sciences, ecology, alternative energy, sustainability, risk management, and local and international regulations. Its collaboration with government ministries and the academia, and its communication of science to non-scientists are a priority in its daily work.

WHAT ARE THE AIMS AND OBJECTIVES OF THE PROJECT?

- 1** To develop research and innovation skills between early stage and experienced researchers, combining social and technological aspects for the sustainable implementation of REL in Southern European countries and Israel.
- 2** To share and integrate multidisciplinary knowledge through international and multisectoral synergies to develop frameworks, processes and operational tools to enhance the spatial planning and social innovation arena for REL and boost relevant policy agendas.
- 3** To investigate and compare data, approaches and processes in Southern European countries and Israel in order to: (a) determine potential commonalities relevant to the subject under investigation (b) exchange this knowledge with the consortium via secondments and (c) transfer this knowledge to a wider audience.
- 4** To produce outputs within the framework of international and intersectoral activities based on the PEARLS project, such as scientific, management and training activities, and dissemination and communication of the results.

WHAT ARE THE RESEARCH QUESTIONS OF THE PROJECT?

- 1** What are the policies and strategies for effective, efficient and sustainable REL implementation in partner countries?
- 2** Who are participating in this process? Where are REL located and why?
- 3** How do the public accept REL implementation in light of their energy behaviour and aspirations?
- 4** What values shape the implementation of spatial planning tools for renewable energy development e.g., economic, social, cultural?
- 5** What are the significant dilemmas voiced in public participation e.g., sustainability issues, conflicts, employment opportunities?
- 6** What networks and practices are developing social innovation tools? What are their best practices?
- 7** What innovations exist to promote and support extended renewable energy landscapes?
- 8** What is the best way to export the applied knowledge expertise on REL in Southern European countries and Israel?

Why is this project needed?

The PEARLS research and innovation project is relevant because globalisation is a dominant policy discourse in the transition to a low carbon economy. The Energy Challenge needs to reinforce public engagement in support of renewable energy. This is often presented as a face-off process, with scant attention paid to the way that cultural approaches towards energy behaviour and public participation contribute to the sustainable implementation of renewable energies.

The overarching objective of this Project is to develop an international and intersectoral network of organisations working in a joint research programme to contribute to the Pan-European Energy Challenge through the implementation of renewable energy best practices. Participants will exchange skills and knowledge that lay the groundwork for key advances in spatial planning and social innovation while strengthening collaborative research among different countries and sectors.

PEARLS Project focuses on how principles avoiding climate change and global warming can be applied to European strategies on public engagement to renewable energy. Despite scientific approach on the promotion of renewable energies and public acceptance based on Not in My Back Yard and Landscape Quality, PEARLS project will develop research capacity in the field of spatial planning and social innovation in Southern European countries. These countries are critical examples of natural resources availability underpinning renewable energies but where less attention to public participation into spatial planning processes is paid. To reinforce knowledge and expertise, new approaches such as Please In My Back Yard, Place Attachment and Territorial Heritage will be developed.

PEARLS interrogates and develops planning and public engagement to deploy renewable energy through questions related to: (a) regional differences in renewable energy resource exploitation; (b) people that can be involved in energy policy initiative support; and (c) whether REL should be developed as focus areas for renewable energy in order for the interaction with the landscape to be better understood.

The nature of the PEARLS partnership means that it will develop strategies for planning and public engagement with all actors in support of REL in beneficiary countries. Through spatial planning and social innovation, the consortium will contribute to achieving REL in Southern European countries and Israel while observing the principles of effectiveness, efficiency, and sustainability in support of the Energy Challenge.

Low Carbon Economy Transition is one of the main challenges that society is facing nowadays. Thus, enhancing the sensitivity on this process, and promoting the advantages that it has for people as individuals and for society as a whole is becoming urgent. This sensitivity must come as result of a better understanding of the new Energy Paradigm. This means that a great involvement of the educational sector is required. On the other hand, it is very important to ensure equal and inclusive participation of local actors in the managing process.

WHAT IS THE ANTICIPATED IMPACT OF THE PROJECT?

1

Generation of stronger awareness that change in the energy model cannot occur without a change in the population's behaviour toward energy.

3

Generation of evidence-based training materials on social innovation and public engagement tools for use in renewable energy development and other research contexts.

5

Stimulation of new trans-methodological approaches to support investigation into social and technological issues by different research and innovation staff.

7

To spark sensitivity to a Low Carbon Economy and the advantages that it has for new life patterns on the individual level and for society.

9

To foster the involvement of young researchers in the dissemination of research results as a complementary way of extending the outreach of their scientific production.

2

Reproduction of public participation schemes to support renewable energy projects developed in countries in Southern Europe and in Israel and to export these to an international audience as good practice.

4

Development of a cadre of researchers, technical staff and policy makers across different sectors and national contexts with in-depth expertise in spatial planning and energy policy.

6

To favour the involvement of the public at large in the Energy Challenge debate (from those who are unfamiliar with it to those who are most in favour of/against renewable energies).

8

To generate new channels of communication between society, researchers and companies by way of everyday formats, such as social networks and Internet video channels.

10

To ensure equal and inclusive participation in events promoted by participant organisations in collaboration with local institutions and authorities in their own countries.

Integrity & Ethics

All research potentially raises ethical issues and this Project is no exception. For that, this research applies without exception the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights and the European Convention on Human Rights and its Supplementary Protocols. The nature of our research work means that relatively few ethical issues are raised and these can be addressed in a relatively straightforward way.

All research partners within the consortium agree to comply with all ethical thinking and legislation within respective countries including those reflected in the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union. Moreover, the Project adheres to the guidelines of the national funding agencies. Rather than thinking about research ethics only in the phase of data collection, the consortium undertakes a comprehensive strategy on ethics by considering ethical issues from the very early phase of research planning. Ethical issues are predominantly relevant for case studies, interviews, fieldwork and dissemination. They include the following spheres:

- All partners will be aware of intellectual property and copyright issues. These issues will be examined thoroughly and resolved by contacting directly the relevant parties before using resources in the project.
- All research partners obtain permission to access sites, written/informed consent, debriefing, explaining the right to refuse/omit answers or withdraw, and consent for interview recording.
- Prospective participants (stakeholders, interviewees, workshop participants) will be given full information in advance about the research's purpose. They are invited to contribute in a variety of ways, dependent on their willingness to be involved.
- All research partners ensure that interview schedules will avoid unnecessarily intrusive questions. Before consent is obtained from respondents and before research begins, all researchers agree to inform prospective participants of the following:
 - Which individuals and organisations, if any, will be permitted access to personal data, and under what circumstances such access will be granted.
 - The purpose for which personal information provided is to be used.
- All researchers agree to work in accordance with equal opportunity policies and ensure that there is no discrimination on the basis of age, gender disability or ethnicity. Furthermore, the data is appropriately used for the purposes of the project and will not be retained for longer than is necessary.
- All researchers envisaged by this project is Social Sciences research concerned with adults specifically those who are engaged in renewable energy landscapes and whose participation is voluntary. As such they should all be able to give their consent for participation informed by a relatively sophisticated understanding of the way that research works and what its implications are. Nevertheless they will be provided with written documentation explaining the aims and objectives of the research and an opportunity to question these.

Gender Balance

Gender balance has been a specific input throughout the entire process. EUSOCLAB envisages gender aspects as a quality of researchers that has to be included in and strengthened throughout the construction of the proposal as the best way to ensure that it is put into effect. The project has taken gender into account in relation to the composition of the partnership, i.e., the coordinator at the University of Seville and the leads in Portugal, Greece and Israel are all female. There are also female representatives from non-academic organisations in Spain (Territorial), Greece (ATTIK) and Israel (SP Interface), and there is also gender balance among Advisory Board representatives. And last but not least, there are female members of the different participant organisations who will be on secondment, thus providing opportunities for both genders to build their capacity via transnational mobility. Gender will also be taken into consideration in everyday processes and transactions. This means that the project will aim to be gender sensitive in relation to the objectives and deliverables and also in terms of inclusive working practices and procedures in focus groups and the choice of people for interview.

Partners

This sub-section contains information about Pearls Project Partners with detailed information by country. Academic and non-academic partners are represented by their logos and titles. Finally, links to their own websites are also included.

A sub-section presents the Advisory Board with information about both the board’s organisation and representatives. Links to own websites are also provided.

PORTUGAL

ICS
INSTITUTO DE CIÊNCIAS SOCIAIS

INSTITUTO DE CIÊNCIAS SOCIAIS
DA UNIVERSIDADE DE LISBOA
<https://www.ics.ulisboa.pt/en>

Coopérnico

COOPERNICO - COOPERATIVA
DE DESENVOLVIMENTO
SUSTENTAVEL CRL
<https://www.coopernico.org/>

ENERCOUTIM
RENEWABLE ENERGY ASSOCIATION

ENERCOUTIM - ASSOCIAÇÃO
EMPRESARIAL DE ENERGIA
SOLAR DE ALCOUTIM
<http://www.enercoutim.eu/>

SPAIN

UNIVERSIDAD DE SEVILLA

UNIVERSIDAD DE SEVILLA
<https://www.us.es/eng>

CLANER
CLUSTER ANDALUZ DE
ENERGIAS RENOVABLES Y
EFICIENCIA ENERGÉTICA

CLUSTER ANDALUZ DE
ENERGIAS RENOVABLES Y
EFICIENCIA ENERGÉTICA
<http://claner.es/en/>

TERRITORIA
ANÁLISIS Y GESTIÓN DEL MEDIO S.L.

TERRITORIA. ANÁLISIS Y
GESTIÓN DEL MEDIO S.L.
<https://territoria.es/>

ITALY

UNIVERSITÀ DI TRENTO

UNIVERSITÀ DEGLI STUDI DI
TRENTO
<https://www.unin.it/en>

GREECE

ARISTOTLE UNIVERSITY OF THESSALONIKI

ARISTOTELIO PANEPISTIMIO
THESSALONIKIS
<https://www.auth.gr/en>

AKKT

AKKT ENGINEERING
<http://www.akkt.gr/root-en.aspx>

GEO SYSTEM HELLAS

GEOSYSTEM HELLAS A.E.
<http://www.geosystems-hellas.gr/en/home/>

TSAKOUMIS
CONSULTANTS & ENGINEERS

TSAKOUMIS CONSULTANTS &
ENGINEERS
<http://www.tsakoumis.com/en/>

ISRAEL

Ben-Gurion University of the Negev

BEN-GURION UNIVERSITY OF
THE NEVEG
<http://in.bgu.ac.il/en/>

SP Interface
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SP INTERFACE
<https://www.sp-interface.com/en/about-us>

ADVISORY BOARD

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ENEA
<http://www.enea.it/en>

UNIVERSITY OF EXETER

EXETER
<https://www.exeter.ac.uk>

._ Our team

This sub-section introduces research staff, professionals and technicians to the public. The aim is to showcase the people who support the project. Links to Research Gate and LinkedIn are provided in most cases.

MARIA JOSÉ PRADOS
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Natalie Samovich
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Miguel Torres García

Territoria, análisis y gestión del medio S.L.

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Rossano Albatici

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Greece

Eva Loukageorgaki

Aristotelio Panepistimio Thessalonikis

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Anastasia Tasopoulou

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Eleni Verani

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Israel

Na'ama Teschner

Ben-Gurion University of the Negev

Rachelle Alterman

The Technion Israel Institute of Technology

Daniel Madar

SP Interface

Hagit Ulanovsky

SP Interface

._ Secondments

The last sub-section presents staff exchange, which is the basis of any MSC RISE project. Detailed information about each secondment beneficiary and experience will be progressively implemented through the website, including:

- Name and Organisation
- Secondment destination
- Photo
- Secondment period)
- Related Work Package

Brief testimonials will be provided by secondees outlining their secondments and recounting personal experiences.

<p>Natalie Samovich ENERCOUTIM (PT) -> University of Seville (SP)</p> <p>FROM JULY 2019 Work Package 2</p>		
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PLANNING AND ENGAGEMENT ARENAS FOR RENEWABLE ENERGY LANDSCAPES

Feel free to contact us for more information about PEARLS Project

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Funded by Marie Skłodowska Curie Actions: H2020 Research Innovation Staff Exchanges (RISE)
Project Number: 778039 - PEARLS

Contact Us

Name

Email Address

Message

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska Curie grant agreement No 778039.

Designed by Circular Creative Agency

Work Packages

This subsection includes a detailed explanation of the seven Work Packages in the Pearls Project. The first six work packages are structured in the same way, in one or two columns,

Information is as follows:

- Focus and WP Participants
- Objectives
- Tasks
- Deliverables (also connected to the RESOURCES repository)
- Related Work Packages and a diagram showing WP relationships.

Below is shown the corresponding section of the Work Package 2 as an example of the structures that WP 1 - 6 will follow.

Sustainable Implementation: Policies and Practices
Work Package 2

PARTICIPANTS

FOCUS

OBJECTIVES

TASKS

DELIVERABLES

WORKING PACKAGES RELATED

Work Package number 7 is devoted to Ethics Requirements and structured around Ethics relating to Humans, Personal Data Protection and Third Countries. This WP7 sub-section ends with a list of Ethics Deliverables.

PARTICIPANTS	FOCUS
	<p>The PEARLS project will require the participation of individuals and local communities (as humans) to study public engagement and social innovation issues. Protection of Personal data will be also related to data collected for case study analysis, in fieldwork and interviews concerning spatial planning policy, social impact assessment and energy behaviour. PEARLS project will apply Horizon2020 ethical standards and guidelines of Horizon2020 regardless of the country in which the research is carried out, as there are some activities in which Third Countries are involved. These activities include (some) research activities carried out in a Third Country and participants or resources from a Third Country. No materials will be imported to/exported from the EU to a Third Country.</p>

OBJECTIVES

01. To be aware of intellectual property and copyright issues (all phases of the project).
02. To obtain permission for doing empirical research (case studies, fieldwork and interviews)
03. To promote participation by providing comprehensive information (case studies, dissemination).
04. To provide Privacy and Confidentiality (case studies, fieldwork and interviews).
05. To handle Data storage and Security.

TASKS

<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Leaflet with detailed information about the project. 3. Data collected stored securely and transferred following security protocols. 5. Safety measures for seconded staff. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Consent forms including or specifying the contact person to whom questions can be addressed. 4. Data Management Plan.
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DELIVERABLES

<p>Informed Consent Forms</p>	<p>Project Information Sheets</p>	<p>Data Protection</p>
<p>Third Countries</p>		

WORKING PACKAGES RELATED

<p>WORKING PACKAGE 1</p>	<p>WORKING PACKAGE 2</p>	<p>WORKING PACKAGE 3</p>	
<p>WORKING PACKAGE 4</p>	<p>WORKING PACKAGE 5</p>	<p>WORKING PACKAGE 6</p>	

Online Atlas

The Online Atlas section is an iterative and participatory tool for PEARLS members. Clicking on markers opens fold-down scrollable worksheets for each case study and reference case that will be available throughout the duration of the project. The purpose of the Online Atlas is to provide an overview of renewable energy landscapes through the regional diversity of participant countries.

The Online Atlas section is still under construction.

Resources

This section includes an information repository. The repository system is based on the Word Press file system. The information contains: Project deliverables; Pearls Project member publications; bibliography; documents and web links. The aim of this repository is to bring project results together in a single place while also hosting them for dissemination and communication. The Project deliverables sub-section provides links to each of the deliverables in their corresponding WPs. Publications include scientific papers, Open Access, Proceedings and other materials produced by Pearls Project members. The last sub-section contains a broad spectrum of working documents based on specific books, working documents in different languages and weblinks displaying PEARLS Project’s regional diversity.

DELIVERABLES

 Interviews				
 Best Current Practices				
 Intranet				
 Third Countries				

PUBLICATIONS BY PEARLS TEAM MEMBERS

 Local Responses to Renewable Energy Development (2018)		
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BIBLIOGRAPHY, DOCUMENTS AND WEBLINKS

 Renewable Energy and Landscape Quality (2018)	
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Good to Know

The website ends with a final section with a two column layout. Good to Know has a dual purpose. From day one the left-hand column will provide up-to-date information about the project's day-to-day and any activities that involve or affect the consortium as a whole. It is a record of the Project that documents any good practices or dysfunctions that may arise and how to work to correct them. The main column on the right will list all the news and events related to the various activities and main achievements of the Project. The is designed to be the key outcome for disseminating project activities to the scientific and R&I community while also providing information targeted at multiple audiences.

Good to know

The University of Seville welcomes the launch of PEARLS Project

Wednesday, July 4, 2018

The Brazilian Pavilion has hosted the launch of the project holding the Kick off Meeting. Academic partners, companies, associations and consultants from Portugal, Spain, Italy, Greece and Israel participated in the event. In addition, this Meeting was attended by PhD students, visiting lecturers and research groups from University of Seville, concerned by the links between Social Sciences and Renewable Energy. After the ceremonial introduction addressed by the Vice-rectory for Innovation and Knowledge Transfer, the European Commission's Science and Knowledge Service of Joint Research Centre in Seville was invited to present the Smart Specialisation Platform on Energy. The synergies between this Smart Platform and the PEARLS Project are evident, so it is expected joint collaborations to take place.

The Kick Off Meeting has enabled the exchange information about the Grant Agreement compliance, the conditions of implementation and funding of the project, and familiarisation with SYGMA platform. Above all though, it has been a splendid opportunity to establish the first face to face contacts between all the participants who will keep a close and productive collaboration along the next four years.

KOM participants and companion people stand up on the roof of the Atarazanas ancient shipyard (Seville, SP)

PEARLS Proposal accepted! It's really happening!

Tuesday, June 5, 2018

The PEARLS beneficiaries have received this message. It has been exactly three months since we submitted PEARLS proposal and they have confirmed us that the proposal is accepted. It was Na'ama Teschner from University of Haifa who sounded the alert. At the same time, there were messages about some phishing attempts coming from the Participant Portal. After a few minutes of surprise, the truth is that PEARLS Project has secured funding. Let's work!

Other News

The US held the official launch of the international action PEARLS, Planning and Engagement Arenas for Renewable Energy Landscapes

<https://investigacion.us.es/noticias/3257>

Archives

September 2018

July 2018

June 2018

April 2018

January 2018

January 2017

Categories

news

secondments

Meta

Log in

Entries RSS

Comments RSS

WordPress.org

PEARLS Proposal submitted. Fingers crossed

Thursday, April 5, 2018

This morning we have submitted the last version of PEARLS proposal into SYGMA Platform, only a few hours before the closure of the 2017 MSC RISE call. We entered the first version in late March. Since then, we have updated a new draft almost every week. We have organised ourselves very well thanks to the work and collaboration from all the Consortium partners. Almudena Arrabal's support with SYGMA Platform and Miguel Torres's graphical design of the information have been very remarkable. The proposal consists of 36 secondments that will be held between thirteen entities from five countries that will focus on six complementary Work Packages. The Steering Committee will support the PEARLS Coordinator. The Consortium will also count with an Advisory Board comprised of Essex University; the Agenzia Nazionale per l'energia ENEA; and the Spanish company Prodiel.

The goal is achieved! : ἀνέριφθω κύβος.

Research and Innovation Staff Exchange (RISE) Coordinators' Day

Friday, January 19, 2018

The MSC-RISE Actions Coordinators have attended the general meeting hosted in Brussels by the Research Executive Agency. There have been two intense sessions where we have been informed about how demanding and extremely competitive has the MSCA RISE 2017 call been. **Only a 20% of the proposals were successful. The objective of the meeting** was to discuss the implementation of the MSCA RISE Grant Agreement and best practices for successful project implementation. Special attention has been given to the requirements of the Grant Agreement; the eligibility conditions for the secondments; and the financial rules.

The meeting provided us with the opportunity of making personal contact with our Project Officer and meeting the other RISE projects coordinators from related fields. The Humanities and Social Sciences Panel are well represented by Southern European countries.

Workshop on Excellent Research Marie Skłodowska-Curie Research and Innovation Staff Exchange

Saturday, January 28, 2017

Eva Loukogeorgaki, Bruno Zanon & Ana Delicado in the Courtyard of Geography and History Faculty at University of Seville (January, 25th 2017).

Finally, earlier this week we have organized the workshop in order to submit a proposal for the forthcoming MSC RISE 2017 call. We have been fortunate enough to meet the academic partners from Lisbon, Trento and Thessaloniki, and to be in contact with Haifa and Esse. On the Spanish side, we are working side by side with Territoria Company. In addition to establish a first contact between the Research Groups on Social Sciences and Architecture at the University of Seville, which work on Renewable Energy.

Until April, 4th we have a lot of work to do: to look for partners from administrative and business environments and NGOs; to refine the structure of a solid proposal; and commit to the Work Packages tasks and secondments if we manage to get the Project's approval.

We have decided our Consortium and Project's name.

We are calling ourselves PEARLS: Planning and Engagement Arenas for Renewable energy Landscapes.

6. Future sections

The project website will be implemented along the project life span. The first action will be the construction of the intranet platform for internal project communication (D6.1: Internal Communication). This will provide key information on the Project and contact information for all partners. It will include the creation, distribution and updating of the project handbook and the implementation and administration of the online collaboration platform.

The second action will be to put in place an online geographic information system (web-GIS) based on Service Oriented Architecture (SOA) (D.4.3: Web GIS Platform), designed and implemented in connection with WP1 and WP6 (D.4.2; D.4.3). The Web-GIS platform will demonstrate the versatility and efficiency of the methodologies and tools for reference case studies and renewable energy landscapes, irrespective of geographical, spatial and/or social factors.

III. Conclusions

This deliverable has presented the communication, dissemination and collaboration infrastructure used by the PEARLS Project. This infrastructure consists of a multifunctional Project Website that contains project research information and implementation; an Online Atlas; a file repository; a contact link and social media presence. The web page was designed and implemented from the scratch based on open source tools (e.g., Django CMS, OwnCloud) and is hosted by the FORTH datacentre. Both the website and file repository are maintained by FORTH and meet all the requirements of the Pearls Project.

This deliverable will be relevant for the Pearls Project's communication strategy. The project website will be used for external communication once results and information have been secured for publications and IPR. Project vision, mission, aims, progress and outcomes will be publicised through the Pearls Project Website and social media activities. Twitter, Instagram and Pinterest are the outlets chosen for the project's Social media presence to date.

The project website will also include a restricted access internal communication platform for partners and GIS tools for mapping and sharing results. The project website will be linked to the USE website (www.us.es) and cross-linked to other beneficiaries' websites.

IV. PEARLS Consortium

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